

Influence of IGBT Switching Behavior on Conducted and Radiated Emissions below 30 MHz

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Abstract— This study examines the influence of switching behavior on conducted and radiated emissions below 30 MHz. A prototype buck converter with a 300 A / 1200 V IGBT module is used, and its switching behavior is modified using a resistive active gate control driver. Time-domain measurements reveal a direct relationship between switching behavior and conducted emissions, as well as magnetic and electric radiated emissions in the frequency range from 10 MHz to 30 MHz. S-shape gate control using an active gate control method effectively reduces initial dV/dt and voltage oscillations. S-shape gate control achieves 22 % to 27 % reduction in switching loss without increasing conducted and radiated emission levels. However, this reduction is not observed from dV/dt -switching loss trade-off. These results show the limitations of using dV/dt only as an EMI indicator. Therefore this paper propose new trade-off indicator, the EMI-switching loss trade-off indicator. The results highlight the importance of advanced control strategies to meet standardized electromagnetic compatibility requirements while optimizing the performance of semiconductor power devices.

Keywords— Active gate control, dV/dt , electromagnetic emissions, IGBT

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, there is an increasing demand of high power semiconductor modules for industrial robotics and electric vehicle applications. Insulated Gate Bipolar Transistors (IGBTs) are widely used for these applications. With the spreading of power electronics equipment in industrial applications, concerns regarding the potential electromagnetic interference (EMI) generated by these systems are growing. Various international standardization organizations have developed electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) standards to control EMI with emission limits. Such standards, including IEC 61800-3 [1] for power drive systems, specify limits for conducted emissions in the frequency ranges from 9 kHz up to 30 MHz, and for electric radiated emissions above 30 MHz.

Recently, the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) has initiated discussions on the standardization of requirements for magnetic radiated emissions below 30 MHz for general power electronic equipment [2]. Consequently, future EMI requirements for power electronics equipment might become stricter. To mitigate EMI, efforts for the development of power semiconductor devices have been focused on improving the dV/dt controllability through

innovations of device structures such as split-gate [3], [4], shield trench [5] and deep trench [6]. These new structures aim to optimize the trade-off between dV/dt controllability and switching loss. Some researchers have investigated relationship between switching behavior and EMI [7], [8], [9]. These studies reported that an S-shaped transient is the most effective behavior for EMI mitigation due to its reduced harmonic content.

Previously cited works focus on the trade-off relationship between dV/dt and switching loss to mitigate EMI. However, while dV/dt provides a convenient proxy for switching performance, it does not directly correlate with the mitigation of EMI. Furthermore, the precise relationship between dV/dt and emission levels, both radiated and conducted is not clear.

Therefore, this study addresses new approach to mitigate EMI by considering dV/dt and emission levels. Active Gate Control methods have been developed to optimize switching behavior [10], [11]. For this study, EMI mitigation is investigated by comparing conventional gate drive and S-shape controlled gate drive, and a resistively controlled active gate driver is designed to modulate switching behavior. Moreover, a novel indicator, the EMI-switching loss trade-off, is proposed.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: In Section II, we describe the methodology employed for EMI measurements including the active gate control topology. Subsequently, Section III presents the analysis results of each EMI mode using both conventional gate drive and S-shape controlled gate drive with active gate control. Then we discussed the trade-off relationship between switching loss, dV/dt and EMI. Next, Section IV summarizes the influence of switching behavior on conducted and radiated emissions below 30MHz.

II. METHODOLOGY

The test object is a prototype buck converter including 300 A / 1200 V IGBT module. The configuration of this buck converter is shown in Fig. 1. The buck converter topology is chosen because of the its simplicity. This allows to minimize circuit complexity influence on the experiments, so the analysis can focus directly on the equipment under test (EUT) and cables between EUT and power supply. The load is an inductor of 0.9 mH and is connected in parallel with Free Wheeling Diode (FWD). The switching frequency is fixed at 1 kHz. The duty cycle is adjusted to maintain a

constant operating current during testing. The basic operating conditions included an input voltage of 600 V, a collector current of 15 A, and a gate resistance (R_g) of 23 Ω . To achieve faster switching, the evaluation is conducted under lower current conditions than the current rating of the IGBT module.

The active gate control driver, shown as a part of Fig. 1, is custom-designed for this study and has eight push-pull output stages which has GaN-HEMT and R_g . The driver adjusts the number of parallel R_g in response to control signals from an FPGA operating at 230 MHz control resolution. This allows for precise switching behavior adjustments at specific timings. The driver implements conventional gate control and S-shape voltage control by modulating the gate signal stepwise, as depicted in Fig. 2. In the case of conventional gate drive, the gate resistance is configured based on typical industrial inverter specifications with a reverse recovery average dV/dt of 4 $kV/\mu s$. For the analysis, the average dV/dt is varied between 1.5 $kV/\mu s$ and 28 $kV/\mu s$. For the S-shape controlled gate drive, R_g is changed as follows. In stage 1, turn on switching starts with typical $R_g = 23 \Omega$. In stage 2, higher $R_g = 100 \Omega$ is applied to prevent the overshoot of V_{ge} and initial dV/dt of reverse recovery. In stage 3, R_g is gradually increased and decreased stepwise. In stage 4, higher $R_g = 100 \Omega$ is applied to prevent the high voltage dV/dt and oscillation. The dV/dt is optimized with R_g profile. The average dV/dt and peak dV/dt are summarized in Table. 1.

Fig. 1. Buck converter for EMI measurement. The buck converter is connected with 1.5 m input cable and 3 m PE cable. An active gate control driver which has eight push pull stages is connected to buck converter.

Fig. 2. Comparison of gate driving topology (a) conventional gate drive and (b) S-shape active gate control. Stable R_g is used for conventional gate drive. R_g is precisely changed during switching transient for active gate control.

Table.1 Switching conditions of the EUT. The switching speed is controlled from average dV/dt of 1.5 $kV/\mu s$ to 28 $kV/\mu s$ by varying R_g . Average dV/dt is obtained from the slope between 10 % and 90 % of V_{ak} . Peak dV/dt is obtained from the maximum slope of V_{ak} .

Gate drive	R_g [Ω]	Reverse recovery dV/dt V_{ak} 10 % to 90 % [$kV/\mu s$]	Reverse recovery dV/dt Peak [$kV/\mu s$]
Conventional gate drive	0.7 Ω	28 $kV/\mu s$	39 $kV/\mu s$
	10 Ω	6 $kV/\mu s$	14 $kV/\mu s$
	23 Ω	4 $kV/\mu s$	9 $kV/\mu s$
	50 Ω	1.5 $kV/\mu s$	4.2 $kV/\mu s$
Active gate control S-shape	R_{g_set1}	4 $kV/\mu s$	6.1 $kV/\mu s$
	R_{g_set2}	3 $kV/\mu s$	5.3 $kV/\mu s$
	R_{g_set3}	2 $kV/\mu s$	4.5 $kV/\mu s$

Measurements are conducted in a 10 m semi anechoic chamber. The measurement setup is shown in Fig. 3. A Line Impedance Stabilization Network (LISN) is used to stabilize the power supply line impedance and keep the same conditions for both conducted and radiated emission measurements. The input and protective earth (PE) cable of EUT are connected to the power supply through the LISN. The cables are bundled and aligned to face the antenna with the shortest distance. The setup maintains a fixed distance of 3 m between the EUT and the antenna.

Fig. 3. Measurement setup for conducted and radiated emissions. The measurement is performed in a semi anechoic chamber.

For emission measurements, a Time Domain Measurement method (shown in Fig. 4) is used instead of conventional frequency-sweep-based spectrum analysis [12], [13]. This method utilizes time-domain data captured by an oscilloscope and then is processed using filters to emulate a measuring receiver. Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) is applied to extract frequency information. It enables frequency analysis over specific time intervals, which is useful for correlating switching waveforms with EMI characteristics in this study. Additionally, the method allows to synchronize the switching events within the measurement time window.

Fig. 4. Block diagram of the multi-channel time-domain EMI measurement system used during the experiments [13].

To analyze the switching behavior of the EUT, R_g is adjusted to modify the switching speed. The switching behavior is shown in Fig. 5. In the switching operations of IGBT and FWD, FWD typically shows a faster switching speed than IGBT. Therefore, this study primarily focuses on analysis of the switching behavior of the FWD. The experiments are performed with average dV/dt ranging from 1.5 $kV/\mu s$ to 28 $kV/\mu s$, representing typical dV/dt for

industrial applications. At the highest dV/dt , voltage oscillations are observed in the voltage and current waveform of FWD. Fig. 5 (b) illustrates the switching behavior under S-shape control. Compared to conventional gate drive at the same average dV/dt , S-shape control suppress initial dV/dt and high voltage dV/dt of reverse recovery during switching transitions. This allows suppression of high frequency components.

(a) Conventional gate drive.

(b) Comparison of conventional gate drive and S-shape controlled gate drive at same average dV/dt ($4 \text{ kV}/\mu\text{s}$). Initial dV/dt and high voltage dV/dt of reverse recovery is suppressed with S-shape modulation.

Fig. 5. Turn on switching behavior of buck converter. Switching speed is modulated with various R_g and S-shape controlled gate drive using active gate control.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 6 shows the emissions of the EUT under different condition in the frequency range from 9 kHz to 30 MHz. First, the analysis of conducted emissions is presented. Conducted emissions can be classified into two modes. One is the differential mode, which is generated by the EUT and flows into the LISN through the positive and negative sides of the input cable. The other is the common mode, which

Fig. 6. Measurement results of conducted and radiated emissions with conventional gate drive changing R_g .

flow through the PE cable and the input cable because of the parasitic capacitance between the IGBT chip and the chassis of the EUT. The analysis indicates that when the average dV/dt increases from $1.5 \text{ kV}/\mu\text{s}$ to $28 \text{ kV}/\mu\text{s}$, significant changes occur in the frequency range from 5 MHz to 30 MHz of the differential mode. In contrast, no notable changes are observed in the common mode within the same frequency range because the frequency components flowing through the parasitic capacitance only contribute to common mode, while conducting current contributes to differential mode.

Next, magnetic and electric radiated emissions between 5 MHz and 30 MHz show similar frequency characteristics to the differential mode of conducted emission above 5 MHz. It is expected that the differential mode of conducted emissions would not have affected to radiated emissions since radiated emissions caused by the differential mode of conducted emissions would be topologically suppressed. This exemplifies that changes in switching behavior affect not only conducted emissions but also magnetic and electric radiated emissions below 30 MHz. In this frequency range, conventionally, only conducted emissions are considered. These results highlight the importance to take into account radiated emissions as well.

Additionally, Fig. 7 compares the results of conventional gate drive and S-shape control at the same average dV/dt . When S-shape control is employed, not only conducted emissions but also radiated emissions are reduced. The result is the same as obtained by increasing gate resistance in conventional gate drive. The EMI reduction is observed in both conducted and radiated emission.

Fig. 7. Comparison of conducted and radiated emissions with S-shape controlled gate drive using active gate control and conventional gate drive at same switching speed (average $dV/dt = 4 \text{ kV}/\mu\text{s}$).

To investigate the relationship between switching loss, dV/dt , and EMI, a comparison of the dV/dt -switching loss and EMI-switching loss trade-off is presented in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9. The turn on switching loss, E_{on} , is calculated from current and voltage waveforms given in Fig. 5. EMI levels are obtained integrating emission spectrum from 5 MHz to 30 MHz and normalized with EMI value at 0.7Ω . The results show that the dependence on gate resistance exhibits a similar trend for both dV/dt -switching loss and EMI-switching loss.

However, in the case of S-shape control, 1% improvement is observed in the average dV/dt -switching loss and 14% in the peak dV/dt -switching loss. The results demonstrate that peak dV/dt exhibits a stronger correlation

with EMI characteristics compared to average dV/dt measurements. Furthermore, EMI measurements show larger improvements, the differential mode-switching loss shows a 22 % reduction, magnetic field-switching loss shows a 24 % reduction because average and peak dV/dt represents only specific frequency components of switching behavior. These results indicate that the dV/dt metric does not fully account for factors critical to EMI analysis, such as localized dV/dt variations or voltage and current oscillations.

These findings suggest that, while dV/dt -switching loss is a useful and convenient indicator, it is insufficient for a comprehensive analysis of switching behavior and EMI. To fully understand the impact of switching dynamics on EMI, it is essential to evaluate EMI itself. Advanced EMI analysis methods will enable more effective design of low emission power devices at the device level.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study examines the influence of switching behavior on conducted and radiated emissions below 30 MHz. While conventional understanding suggests switching behavior affects only conducted emissions below 30 MHz, our results reveal a relationship between switching behavior and both conducted and radiated emissions, particularly in the frequency range of 10 MHz to 30 MHz.

The S-shape gate control using an active gate control method achieves a 22 % to 27 % reduction in switching loss without increasing conducted and radiated emission levels. However, this improvement is not observed in the traditional dV/dt -switching loss trade-off. It demonstrates the limitations of using dV/dt only as an EMI indicator. To address this limitation, we introduce an EMI-switching loss trade-off indicator that evaluates the relationship between switching behavior and emission levels. This indicator enables accurate analysis of switching loss reduction while maintaining EMI performance. This EMI-switching loss trade-off indicator is expected to be applicable to other power devices such as SiC MOSFETs, which operate at higher switching speeds. These findings emphasize the importance of considering EMI perspective when analyzing the relationship between switching behavior and conducted and radiated emissions.

As requirements for radiated emissions below 30 MHz become more stringent, advanced control strategies will be crucial for optimizing the performance of semiconductor power devices while meeting electromagnetic compatibility requirements.

Fig. 8. Comparison of dV/dt – switching loss E_{on} trade-off relationship.

Fig. 9. Comparison of EMI – switching loss E_{on} trade-off relationship.

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